

The BMF analytics title at Harvard University HOLLIS

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The methodology title on BMF analytics is now in its third year of service to our research community, enabling many researchers to implement their research pursuits.

We recently stumbled upon its listing on the Harvard University Library HOLLIS system as shown in the photo below.

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Illustration: BMF analytics on HOLLIS [1].

Its appearance at the Harvard University HOLLIS helps boost our confidence and strengthen our determination to bring its uses to the community, together with the computing capabilities of the *bayesvl* R package [2].

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (Eds.). (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. https://hollis.harvard.edu/permalink/f/1mdq5o5/TN_cdi_unpaywall_primary_10_2478_9788367405119

[2] La VP, Vuong QH. (2019). bayesvl: Visually learning the graphical structure of Bayesian networks and performing MCMC with ‘Stan’. <https://cran.r-project.org/package=bayesvl>

